

Reassessing the great compression among top earners: The overlooked role of taxation and self-employment

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides new estimates of wage inequality in the United States from 1918 to 1949, leveraging a novel top-income methodology that integrates both tax records and census data. Our analysis reveals no sustained decline in wage inequality before the Second World War but a marked decrease during the war years. This decline was driven primarily by stagnation among the top 1 % of earners and significant wage growth at the lower end of the income distribution. However, the relative underperformance of the top earners was largely influenced by a major compositional shift triggered by unprecedented increases in corporate and personal income tax rates. These tax changes led to a shift in business preferences toward partnerships, resulting in a substantial transition from salaried employment to self-employment. This shift, previously overlooked in inequality studies, resulted in a 30 % overestimation of wage compression, significantly altering the wage distribution dynamics of the 1940s.

1. Introduction

Wage inequality in the United States declined substantially in the first half of the 20th century, during what has been termed the Great Compression (Goldin and Margo 1992). This phenomenon is of vital interest, as it stands out as one of the primary catalysts in the broader process of reducing income inequality during this period (Lindert and Williamson 2016, 194). While the general patterns of earnings dispersion are relatively well documented, the underlying causes of these shifts remain less understood. One of the main arguments of the Great Compression process is that the expansion in higher education reduced the earnings premium of high-skilled white-collar workers. However, this hypothesis is mostly derived from comparing the evolution of wages by occupation and the returns from college education. The fortunes of the small minority of the highest-paid workers have been largely unexplored, which is a critical omission to fully understand wage inequality.

The main objective of this paper is to shed light on the evolution of top earners—the top 5 % of the wage distribution—during the Great Compression. Specifically, we seek to answer three related questions. First, whether the decline in their earnings premium was a long and gradual process or a sudden shock triggered by the Second World War (WW2). Second, whether this amounted to an absolute or a relative decline in income levels at the top. Third, the extent to which this shift can be attributed to changes in the composition of top earners, particularly in terms of employment status (from salaried positions to self-employment), which may have contributed to wage compression.

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Until now, answering these questions has been extremely difficult given the lack of consistent and comparable data series. As a contribution to this field, this paper provides new estimates of top wages for this period, derived from tax statistics and matched with data from the 1940 and 1950 censuses. Our approach builds on the work of [Piketty and Saez \(2003, 2007\)](#) on top wages, but with more refined adjustments regarding individuals, exempted incomes, and extending the dataset to earlier years. More importantly, by making use of the detailed sociodemographic data of the census and using the newly published linked records of individuals from the 1940 and 1950 census microdata, we provide a more accurate calibration of potential shifts in the employment status of highly paid workers during this critical period.

The results of this paper confirm that wage inequality was high in the 1920s and 1930s, with no evidence of a secular decline. Later, during the Second World War, real wage growth among the top 1 % stagnated, contributing significantly to the Great Compression. However, this abrupt shock is more complex than previously thought. While compensation for highly paid occupations lagged overall wage growth in the economy, the stagnation in earnings was intensified by a significant compositional effect that resulted from a shift in the employment status of many highly paid workers, who moved from salaried positions to self-employment. The primary driver behind this turn was the substantial rise in corporate and personal income taxes in the early 1940s, which shifted business preferences regarding their legal status. A growing preference for partnerships, coupled with a relative decline in the number of corporations, altered the employment status of many highly paid workers from salaried to self-employed. This shift, which has rarely been documented until now, further contributed to the reduction in wage inequality.

This paper does not contest the significance of the Great Compression but emphasizes that most of this phenomenon stemmed from a substantial upsurge in wages at the lower end of the distribution, whereas the situation at the top exhibited greater complexity. The traditional top wage metric shows that top earnings declined in real terms. However, considering the expansion of the employed population and the transition to self-employment, the top 1 % experienced more substantial growth in their earnings. This has resulted in an overestimation of the decline in inequality during the 1940s by approximately 30 %. Furthermore, this perspective highlights that the economic boom of the 1940s primarily favored low-wage earners, although every cohort of workers eventually experienced a rise in real earnings owing to advancements in productivity.

This paper contributes to several strands of the economic history literature. First and foremost, it adds to the growing body of studies on the Great Compression, both those studies carried at the national level ([Goldin and Margo 1992](#); [Goldin and Katz 2010](#); [Autor et al., 2020](#)) and those focusing on specific highly paid groups, such as the financial industry ([Philippon and Reshef 2012](#)) or corporate executives ([Piketty and Saez 2003](#); [Frydman and Saks 2010](#); [Frydman and Molloy 2012](#)). Our findings depart in two significant ways from these earlier studies. First, in contrast to Goldin, Autor and Katz's framework, our analysis places greater emphasis on and expands the demand-driven factors—particularly business creation and tax incentives. We argue that these factors played a more significant role than previously thought. Furthermore, our results suggest that several previously cited factors, such as increased government regulations, a general decline in risk-taking activities, or the indirect effects of unionization, are insufficient to fully explain the stagnation in real earnings at the top. By incorporating the shift in employment status among top earners, we highlight how this group was more adaptive to the changing institutional environment of the 1940s than previously acknowledged.

This paper also makes a major methodological contribution to the inequality literature. In the last 20 years, there has been an impressive expansion in studies concerning top incomes, which combine tax data and national accounts to build estimates ([Atkinson and Piketty 2007, 2010](#)). These results are sometimes regarded as benchmark series, although more recently, their accuracy has been questioned in several ways ([Geloso et al. 2022](#); [Auten and Splinter 2023](#)). The literature on top incomes has also been unable to reconcile its findings with studies that rely on data sources that classify workers and their income according to their industry, occupation, race or sex, since this information is typically missing in tax returns. For this reason, the social tables perspective for historical periods has also grown substantially ([Gómez León and De Jong 2019](#); [Lindert and Williamson 1983](#); [Milanovic, Lindert, and Williamson 2011](#); [Modalsli 2015](#)). Our approach emphasizes that in countries with well-developed tax and census systems, it is possible to reconcile both perspectives and provide a more elaborate analysis. In the case of top earners, our analysis shows that it is crucial to use tax data to circumvent the top coding inherent in the census but also that it is necessary to rely on this last source to have a better understanding of labor incomes, adjusting for several key dimensions (occupation, household composition, years of education, etc.) and to factor in job mobility across time.

Finally, this study improves our understanding of the relationships among tax frameworks, business institutions and inequality. In recent years, a growing number of scholars in the United States have analyzed how the tax reforms enacted in the 1980s caused substantial variation in the legal form of businesses ([DeBacker and Prinsinzano 2015](#)), with a relative decline in the number of traditional corporations and an increase in the number of closely held business firms (such as S-corporations). This change has been recognized as having profound implications for our understanding of 21st-century capitalism ([Smith et al. 2019](#)). Our study, which highlights that there was a similar shift in the 1940s, aims to emphasize that scholars should also rethink the nature of capitalism and entrepreneurship in a period that has traditionally been identified as the golden era of the modern corporation ([Langlois 2023, 409–12](#)). Consequently, more attention should be given to the nature and relationship between small businesses and the partnership form.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. [Section 2](#) outlines the methodology and data sources, detailing the process of deriving wage estimates from income tax tabulations. Moreover, we explain how these figures can be reconciled with other sources, such as the population census. [Section 3](#) presents the main results, followed in [Section 4](#) by a specific discussion on managers, the shift in tax incentives and its effect on the upsurge in self-employed high earners. This section is divided into three parts: the first part provides qualitative evidence on the relationship between tax increases, tax avoidance, and the growth of self-employment; the second part presents several models that demonstrate the positive correlation between the tax burden and the likelihood of transitioning to self-employment; and the final part offers new estimates of labor inequality that incorporate the earnings of the self-employed. Finally,

Section 5 provides a brief conclusion.

2. Data and methods

Wage inequality has been a subject of substantial research in U.S. economic history. However, from a methodological standpoint, a noticeable disparity exists between studies conducted before and after 1940. This difference can largely be attributed to the 1940 national census, which, for the first time, recorded data on wages and education, augmenting the traditional variables of age, sex, occupation, and industry. In previous periods, information was more limited, so scholars had to rely primarily on census employment figures supplemented by separate records on pay for representative occupations from various sources, such as state-level census records and business surveys (Goldin and Katz 2010).

This paper, however, argues that starting in 1918, tax records provide a reliable and consistent method for calculating wages at the upper end of the distribution and for deriving metrics on wage inequality. Using a novel methodology that follows the path of a growing number of studies that have revised the first estimates provided almost two decades ago (Jaworski and Niemesh 2018; Geloso and Magness 2020; Fisher-Post 2020; Geloso et al. 2022; Auten and Splinter 2023), these estimates are harmonized with 1940–50 census records. This approach offers a more comprehensive source for analyzing the dynamics of top wage inequality during the interwar period. Ultimately, our methodology aims to produce the most precise estimates possible, focusing on individuals rather than tax units—the latter having been the traditional measurement in studies of top inequality. A summarized explanation of the adjustments is provided in the rest of this section, with a detailed discussion available in the Appendix.

Following the literature on top incomes, which was pioneered by Kuznets (1953) and further developed by other scholars (Atkinson and Harrison 1978; Piketty 2001), we start by measuring the upper tail of the wage distribution through tax records. The share of the top X percent is obtained by dividing the cumulative wages above the corresponding threshold by the total wage bill, as shown in Eq. (1).

$$\text{Wage share of top } x\% = \frac{\sum_{i=nx/100}^n w_{xi}}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad (1)$$

where w_i is the wage of individual i , x is the selected percentile, and w_{xi} is the wage of individuals who are above the threshold. The employed population and income denominators are defined according to the U.S. National Income and Product Accounts (NIPA) from 1929 onward and prior to that date by using the series of Piketty and Saez (2007, 210) built from the national accounts of Kuznets (Kuznets 1954). In this approach, wages omitted from tax returns (such as in-kind payments or unreported compensation) are implicitly accrued to the bottom of the distribution.

Our estimates on top wage groups are primarily based on the data extracted from personal income tax records. This task is especially daunting given the absence of microdata, which only became available in the U.S. in the early 1960s. Thus, we depend on tabulations and interpolation techniques. This is usually performed by employing Pareto interpolation techniques; however, in our paper, these methods are carried out by incorporating the generalized Pareto curves of Blanchet, Fournier, and Piketty (2022).¹ Piketty and Saez (2003) provided their estimates from 1927 onward using the available information in the *Statistics of Income* (SOI). Table 1 presents a summarized version of the original tabulated data, which shows the extreme details on the number of wage earners and their distribution among those with more than \$5000 in net income (i.e., roughly speaking, those within the top 1 %). For all other returns, information is much more limited; therefore, Piketty and Saez had to estimate the wage distribution on the basis of some assumptions about the number of earners (i.e., Column B in Table 1) and the relative distribution of wages within each bracket (Column C).

We begin by revising and extending these estimates. Our amendments, which are inspired by the largely forgotten contribution of official authorities after the Second World War (Office of Business Economics, 1953), have four main objectives. First, we improve the imputation method for the distribution of wages that fit below the top 1 % of earners. This involves calculating the number of wage earners per income bracket via detailed tax reports from the 1930s and 1940s and applying a new approach, called the *Constant Lorenz Curve Transformation*, which avoids the assumption of identical rankings between wage and net income distributions—a limitation of Piketty and Saez's (2003) approach. Second, we extend the estimates back to 1918 by leveraging the close relationship between the relative number of wage earners (by income bracket) and wage variance. Third, we shift from the traditional unit of measurement (tax units) to individuals, which seems to be more correct conceptually and allows for harmonization with microdata from the 1940 and 1950 censuses. To achieve this, we individualize wages in joint returns by using the information derived from the 1940 census. Finally, following the revision of Geloso et al. (2022), we include wages exempt from federal income tax, most notably the earnings of local and state employees until 1938. All steps are outlined in detail in the Appendix.

In this paper, we provide results on the top 1 % (above the 99th percentile) and the next 4 % (from the 95th to 99th percentile) of wage earners. Both groups are well covered in income tax statistics since they almost always fit above the minimum filling threshold. We deliberately avoid extending our analysis beyond these percentiles (e.g., up to the top 10 %), as this would entail projecting estimates toward a group of workers that is not observed in the original source prior to 1939. The wage share of the bottom 95 % is calculated as a residual. We limit our analysis by using tax records up to 1947, since the substantial tax reform enacted the year after

¹ As a robustness check, a nonparametric density estimation method based on the maximum entropy principle (Akira et al., 2023) is employed for estimating the top 1 % wage shares yielding similar results. However, this method may be more suitable for certain postestimation analyses that were not conducted in this paper.

Table 1
Cross-tabulation of income tax return reporting wages, 1936.

Income brackets (net income)	Number of returns (A)	Returns with wages (B)	Wage brackets (C)											
			All	1	1000	2000	3000	4000	5000	10,000	15,000	25,000	50,000	100,000
1	277,803	Not available	Not available											
1000	2111,789													
2000	1317,752													
3000	729,755													
4000	299,389													
5000	440,886	287,378	100 %	5 %	4 %	5 %	6 %	9 %	66 %	4 %	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
10,000	105,582	64,732	100 %	6 %	4 %	4 %	4 %	4 %	28 %	44 %	6 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
15,000	71,067	42,353	100 %	7 %	4 %	3 %	3 %	3 %	18 %	23 %	36 %	3 %	0 %	0 %
25,000	41,137	23,940	100 %	8 %	4 %	3 %	3 %	2 %	13 %	13 %	25 %	28 %	1 %	0 %
50,000	13,620	7772	100 %	10 %	3 %	3 %	2 %	2 %	10 %	10 %	17 %	26 %	17 %	1 %
100,000	4719	2727	100 %	14 %	5 %	3 %	2 %	2 %	7 %	7 %	12 %	20 %	18 %	11 %

Source: SOI (1936).

increased the number of joint returns and complicates the task of accruing wages within couples. Nonetheless, as we will argue, the 1940 and 1950 censuses provide comparable data on the wage distribution to study the end of this period, allowing us to integrate imputed wage distributions with census data via the IPUMS sample and the full population database (Helgertz et al. 2024; Ruggles et al. 2021, 2024).

A comparison between the 1940 IPUMS 1 % sample and the estimates derived from personal income tax records serves both as an introduction to the matching procedure and a robustness check on the representativeness of our approach. Table 2 shows the estimates for the 95th to 99th percentiles in 1939, comparing our imputed tax tabulation results with reported census wages. The estimates are closely aligned, with only minor discrepancies, such as a \$99 difference at the 97th percentile (\$3000), due to rounding effects in census records. Remarkably, the key percentiles of interest are nearly identical, with a \$4 difference at the 95th percentile and a \$27 difference at the 99th percentile.

Given the high comparability between these two data sources, we propose combining them for a more comprehensive analysis. This integrated approach provides richer insights into top-earning wage cohorts by incorporating socioeconomic data from census records, such as age, sex, race, occupation, and industry, which are missing from tax statistics. Additionally, newly matched census crosswalk data enable individuals to be linked across different censuses, providing valuable longitudinal microdata. By integrating income tax data, we also address the limitations of previous studies that relied solely on census records and faced challenges from decennial frequency and top-coded observations. This enhanced approach enables a more thorough examination of the wage distribution among high earners during the interwar period.

3. Wage inequality 1918–1949

This section provides a long-term view of the period analyzed. We focus first on top wage metrics derived from tax statistics for consistency and then uncover the main trends in inequality. Our analysis starts with an examination of the wage shares (Fig. 1A, 1B and 1C). The shares evolved during the interwar period (1918–39) within some close bounds, as illustrated by the fact that the top 1 % wage share was between 8 % and 10 % of the total, and the next 4 % ranged between 10 % and 12 %. Overall, these are relatively high levels compared with those in other countries in which top wage shares have been estimated (Piketty 2001; Moriguchi and Saez 2008; Atkinson and Voitchovsky 2011), although not as extreme as those observed in the United States since the 1990s.

The top 1 % wage share increased considerably in the 1920s (especially in the years 1924–8), which was reversed at the start of the Great Depression (1929–33). The share of the next 4 % group hardly increased during the 1920s boom, as it hovered at approximately 11 % of the wage bill. In the first years of the 1930s, the next 4 % group experienced a very significant increase that was partly reversed in the second half of the decade. By construction, the bottom 95 % commanded a dwindling share of wages from the early 1920s to 1933 and later stagnated during the rest of the Depression. The three series unequivocally show that, by far, the largest shock occurred during the Second World War. In this relatively short time period, the top 1 % share declined by almost 2 percentage points and stabilized at a permanently lower level. The next 4 % group also experienced a decline, though with a weaker permanent effect, and by 1946–7, its share was roughly at the same level as that in the mid-1920s. Finally, the bottom 95 % undoubtedly benefited the most from the war years.

Wage shares, in either definition, reveal more about the relative evolution of each group than about their absolute performance. To illustrate the evolution of earnings in relation to the business cycle, we calculate real average wages via two definitions: standard and fixed-group. While the first definition is based on the percentiles resulting from the number of employed workers in each year, for the fixed-group share, a permanent number of individuals is selected, and their respective average wage is computed (Krolage et al., 2022). Implicitly, this metric works under the assumption that sudden changes in employment fall entirely on the left tail of the distribution. In this paper, the fixed groups of the top 1 % and next 4 % are constructed relative to the employed population in 1939 (39.6 million wage and salary workers). This is a good reference point and of a similar order of magnitude to that of 1929 (37.7 million employees), roughly speaking, the maximum employed population of the interwar period.

Fig. 2A and 2B display the mean real wages for the top wage groups and provide some relevant conclusions. First, in both cases, the difference between the average earnings in the standard and fixed-group measures is especially relevant in critical junctures, such as the Second World War or the Great Depression. In the average wage derived through the standard shares, the actual wage growth of top earners in periods of net job creation is typically underestimated. The opposite happens in periods of job destruction. In contrast, the fixed-group share provides an upper bound in these periods.

Studying the real wages of the top 1 % of earners is especially relevant, as their real earnings were significantly more volatile than

Table 2
Estimated 95th to 99th percentiles via the SOI and census data, 1939.

Figures in current dollars		
Percentile	SOI	Census
95	2504	2500
96	2809	2750
97	3099	3000
98	3611	3600
99	5027	4992

Source: SOI, IPUMS.

Fig. 1. Wage shares for the Top 1 %, Next 4 % and bottom 95 %.
 Sources: SOI. Note: The wage shares of the top 1 %, next 4 % and bottom 95 % correspond, respectively, to groups between p99–100, p95–99, and p0–95.

those of the next 4 % group, which enjoyed a much stronger downward rigidity. The real wages of the top 1 % increased substantially in the 1920s (growing by approximately 30 % in the fixed-group definition) and then stagnated for the following two decades. The two shocks in the Great Depression and the Second World War are probably not as surprising, although a comparison of the two definitions

Fig. 2. Average real wages for the top 1 %, next 4 % and bottom 95 % percentiles (1929 = 100). Sources: SOI Notes: The fixed-group (FG) shares have been constructed relative to the employed population of 1939. By definition, this metric is equal to the standard share in this year. The average wage for the bottom 95 % of the wage-earning population cannot be calculated through the fixed-group definition. Instead, we proxy its evolution by adding the number of unemployed individuals to the bottom 95 % of the wage-earning population in each year.

reveals a more complete perspective on the factors at play. From 1929 to 1933, the real earnings of the top 1 % group declined substantially (by 13 % in the standard definition or by 20 % in the fixed group), thereby making the Great Depression the greatest negative shock in earnings, both in terms of depth and persistence. In the war years, the difference between the two metrics is also quite pronounced. Between 1939 and 1947, the real earnings of the top 1 % declined by 5 % according to the standard metric, whereas in the fixed-group definition, real earnings grew by 5 %. Thus, the Second World War was not such a negative shock for top earners, but the difference lies in the radically different economic context, as shown by the performance of other groups.

The trends in the real earnings of the next 4 % are substantially different. Overall, under both scenarios, this group of workers shows better relative performance at times of economic crisis, such as in the 1920–1 recession, and even more significantly, at the start of the Great Depression (1929–33). In fact, in the fixed group definition, real salaries hardly decreased, indicating that this group was particularly isolated in terms of wage cuts at times of crisis. Again, the growth in earnings in the fixed group gauge was greater than that in the standard one, especially from 1939 to 1943. This evidence elucidates that the war-induced boom did not particularly benefit this group and that their wages underperformed the broader economy.

For the bottom 95 %, one cannot construct a fixed-population measure; however, a relatively good proxy is to compute a mean wage by dividing the aggregate compensation among wage earners and unemployed persons. The logic behind this exercise is that a substantial part of the adjustment of the bottom takes place through redundancies, and the average wage that results from counting the unemployed better reflects the actual earnings of the potentially working population. This metric may also better reflect a situation with a significant reduction in working hours and an increase in part-time employment, which was characteristic of the Great Depression (Bernanke 1986). Most likely, workers were entering and exiting the labor market more fluidly in this scenario (Hatton and Thomas 2010, 476).

Fig. 2C depicts the real earnings in these two scenarios. The difference between them is not relevant to identifying the absence of significant growth in earnings during the Roaring Twenties (1924–9), but it helps to better understand the enormous decline of the Great Depression. Real wages experienced a decline of 30 % relative to the standard definition, whereas accounting for unemployment resulted in an approximate 50 % decrease. The substantial disparity between the two figures underscores the significance of unemployment's influence on labor market adjustments during the crisis (Hanes 2000, 1433). These declines marked the most significant losses for any group and were not reversed until the United States entered the Second World War in 1941. Finally, it is crucial to note the remarkable recovery observed toward the period's conclusion, with earnings soaring by >50 %.

In summary, both standard and alternative measures confirm the overall decrease in wage inequality during this period. However, this trend was far from steady. The Roaring Twenties increased inequality, especially due to the greater increase in the wages of the top 1 % and the stagnancy of the bottom. Afterward, the top group suffered from large losses during the Great Depression, but the impact of rising unemployment and the downward rigidity of the wages of the next 4 % group prevented a reduction in wage inequality. The decisive turning point occurred when the U.S. entered the Second World War. Real wages at the top stagnated, and the gains of the bottom 95 % significantly outperformed the rest. This analysis confirms that while the Great Depression caused relevant changes, the war completely transformed wage inequality in the U.S.

4. The decline in the top 1 % wage share during WW2

4.1. Managers, business forms and taxation

This section combines the results from the previous one with other tax records and census microdata to explore the decline in the top 1 % wage share during the 1940s. Our analysis is built on two relatively simple yet rarely combined arguments. First, we assert that corporate officers constituted the primary group within the top 1 % of wage earners. This group included not only executives from

Table 3
Socioeconomic characteristics of wage earners, 1939 and 1949.

Group	Variables	All wage earners		Top 1 %	
		1939	1949	1939	1949
Demographic	Male	72 %	67 %	97 %	94 %
	Race, white	90 %	89 %	100 %	99 %
Education	Years of schooling	9.1	9.8	12.9	12.9
	College (% with)	12 %	15 %	51 %	52 %
Occupation	Professionals	7 %	7 %	22 %	19 %
	Managers and officials	5 %	5 %	51 %	46 %
	Clerical	12 %	12 %	6 %	4 %
Industry	Sales workers	7 %	6 %	13 %	15 %
	Manufacturing	27 %	26 %	32 %	32 %
	Transport	8 %	8 %	7 %	6 %
	Trade	15 %	16 %	17 %	26 %
	Finance	3 %	3 %	14 %	8 %
	Professional services	7 %	7 %	11 %	7 %
	Public sector	5 %	6 %	6 %	5 %
Other	36 %	34 %	14 %	16 %	

Source: IPUMS, 1940 and 1950 censuses.

publicly listed companies but also a significant number of officers from small and medium-sized enterprises, where they often held positions as controlling shareholders. Second, we argue that the unprecedented increase in tax pressure—both corporate and individual—created strong incentives to adopt various tax optimization strategies. One of the most prominent schemes involved changing a company’s legal status from a corporation to a partnership, thus avoiding the sharp increase in corporate tax rates. As a result, many executives transitioned from being salaried employees (i.e., officers) to self-employed workers (i.e., partners).

The starting proposition—the enormous overrepresentation of corporate officers at the top—can be easily documented with the 1940 and 1950 censuses. As shown in Table 3, prior to World War II, managers and officials made up nearly half of the top percentile, followed by professionals (22 %) and sales workers (13 %). A decade later, the occupational mix had barely shifted. Although the share of managers had declined slightly, they still comprised 46 % of the top 1 %. Compared with the overall occupational distribution of the U.S. workforce, managers remained the most overrepresented group at the very top. Notably, in terms of industries, no major sector displayed such a pronounced overrepresentation in the top percentile.

The absence of wage data in earlier censuses limits our ability to perform this type of analysis for previous years. However, one intuitive way to explore the evolution of this group is by looking at the number of corporate officers on the basis of corporate tax statistics. As illustrated in Fig. 3, the trends and levels align closely with those observed in census data for managers overall, which includes not only corporate officers but also other roles, such as store managers and public officials. The data provide further confirmation of one of the factors potentially driving the evolution in the top 1 % wage share. The greatest growth in the number of corporate officers occurred in the 1920s, followed by stagnation in the 1930s. Interestingly, despite overall economic growth, the early 1940s witnessed a decline in the number of corporate officers, only for their ranks to rise again in the second half of the decade.

During this period, the demand for managerial salaried workers appears to have been differently from other white-collar occupations, which was the focus of the influential work by Goldin and Katz (2010, 2020). At the beginning of the century, both groups could be considered “noncompeting” owing to their limited numbers and significant barriers to entry. However, the number of managers did not grow as rapidly between 1920 and 1950. Entry into managerial roles was likely influenced more by demand-side factors, such as the creation of new businesses, than by supply-side factors—e.g., the expansion of higher education. These different drivers may help explain the divergence between the numbers of the two groups.

This brings us to the second major argument: the 1940s saw a historical shift in business preferences regarding legal status. In this context, it is useful to focus on businesses with at least two or more parties—namely, corporations and partnerships—and to exclude the larger number of sole proprietorships. A simple indicator of the preference between these business forms is shown in Fig. 4A. The results indicate that, before World War II, corporations were the dominant business form, leading to the creation of new businesses, particularly in the 1920s. In contrast, partnerships played a marginal role—aside from their concentration in specific sectors such as professional services, finance, and real estate—and decreased in relevance from 1925 to the mid-1930s. The 1940s, however, saw an unprecedented shift. While the number of corporations declined during the war years, partnerships surged, more than tripling and becoming the most common form of business organization.

The most plausible explanation for this shift lies in changes to the tax code, as reflected in the fluctuations in the average effective

Fig. 3. Number of salaried managers (Decennial population census) and corporate officers (Corporate Tax), 1918–1950.

Source: IPUMS decennial microdata (Ruggles et al. 2021), and Statistics of Income (United States, Bureau of Internal Revenue. Various years, 1916).

Fig. 4A. Number of active corporations and partnerships, in thousands, 1920–1950.

Fig. 4B. Average effective corporate and personal income tax rate, in percentage, 1920–1950.

Note: The average corporate tax rate is obtained by dividing the corporate tax rate by positive net income. The average tax rate in the personal income tax has been obtained by dividing the personal income tax by the estimated adjusted gross income of all U.S. households, irrespective of whether they filed a tax return (Geloso et al. 2022). Since for most of the period, the vast majority of the population paid no federal personal income taxes, the average rate is close to 0. **Sources:** SOI, NIPA and Geloso et al. (2022).

corporate and personal income tax rates, which closely align with the surge in partnerships (Fig. 4B). The average effective corporate tax rate, which had remained nearly constant at approximately 13 % between 1922 and 1938, more than tripled to 55 % by 1943, before stabilizing at approximately 30–35 % after World War II. In addition to these corporate tax hikes, individuals also faced an

unprecedented increase in personal income taxes, a topic that has been the focus of much recent historical research (Torregrosa-Hetland and Sabaté 2022).

Partnerships have traditionally benefited from more favorable tax treatment than corporations, as they are exempt from corporate taxes, with profits being accrued directly to each individual partner. Nonetheless, the extent of this tax advantage depends on the interplay between corporate and personal income taxes. During the 1920s and 1930s, the tax advantage for unincorporated businesses was relatively modest because of the combination of low statutory corporate tax rates, generous personal income tax exemptions (particularly for married couples), and the ability to deduct officers' compensation from corporate profits, which minimized the tax burden on small corporations. As documented in a special enquiry of the Department of Commerce (McConnell 1945), most small corporations reported a negligible net income, especially when a few shareholders agreed to pay themselves a relatively high salary (as a percentage of profits), leaving only a portion of the remaining profits to be distributed as dividends.

In contrast, in the early 1940s, the introduction of corporate surtaxes and the increasing burden of higher personal income taxes gave small corporations with a limited number of shareholders strong incentives to change their legal status. By doing so, they could not only completely avoid corporate taxes but also include nonactive or "silent" partners—individuals who contributed capital but did not participate in the business's operations. The flexibility of tax and business laws encouraged owners of closely held businesses to include family members—spouses, children, and other relatives—as partners, reducing overall tax liability by splitting total business income into different earners.

Indeed, tax legislation evolved to address concerns about whether the increasing number of partnerships, particularly those formed by family members, represented a legitimate business model or a tax avoidance strategy. In 1946, the Supreme Court ruled that a spouse who had not contributed original capital or provided essential services to the business could not be considered a genuine partner (¹Commissioner v. Tower, 1946). This ruling established an important precedent for evaluating family partnerships in tax matters, prompting increased scrutiny by the IRS and a rise in litigation in this area (Baldin Martin, 1950; Lifton, 1952). Only two years later, in 1948, the Supreme Court sought to clarify the principles, rejecting an overly literal interpretation of the "original capital" and "vital services" criteria that had been applied in some subsequent cases (Porter, 1952). A new ruling introduced a more flexible, fact-based approach to determining the validity of family partnerships, emphasizing the intent of the parties (Baldin Martin, 1950).

The significance of these legal battles waned after the 1948 tax reform, which for the first time introduced the principle of equal income splitting for married couples. This reform effectively extended the tax benefits to a broader range of taxpayers, particularly wage earners. Although tax reform and increased IRS controls reduced the incentives to continue dissolving corporations in favor of partnerships, they did not encourage a return to the pre-1939 situation. As a result, the 1940s must be seen as a unique turning point in small businesses' preferences regarding their legal status.

4.2. The 1940 shift from salaried to self-employed

The previous section summarized the main argument and aggregate indicators that point to the potential shift in the employment status of a significant number of corporate officers in the 1940s. However, no research has quantitatively demonstrated the relationship between the partnership boom and the increase in taxes during this decade. The recent release of matched census crosswalk data for the 1940 and 1950 censuses provides an ideal opportunity to test this hypothesis (Helgertz et al. 2024).

In our analysis, we focus on individuals who reported wages in the 1940 census and were still earning wages or business income ten years later. This cohort comprises approximately 14.2 million individuals (approximately 31 % of total employees). Among this group, we restrict the analysis to those that provide information across all variables (12.3 million) and identify those who remained wage earners (10.5 million, including 120,617 who were in the top 1 % of wage earners in 1939) and those who transitioned to self-employment (1.9 million, of whom 37,222 were also in the top 1 % in 1939). Using a logit model, we analyze the sociodemographic and economic factors influencing the likelihood of transitioning from wage employment to self-employment between 1939 and 1949.

The benchmark model is specified as follows:

$$P(\text{Self} = 1 | X) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{Tax1940}_i + \beta_2 * \text{Married}_i + \beta_3 * \text{Nchildren}_i + \beta_4 * \text{Wage}_i + \dots + \beta_n * X_{ni})}} \quad (2)$$

where *Self* is a binary variable that takes a value of 1 if an individual transitioned from wage employment in 1939 to self-employment by 1949, and 0 if they remained a wage earner. The key explanatory variable is the estimated taxes the individual would have paid in 1940 on their 1939 income.² The model also includes factors that could influence the decision to form a partnership, such as marital status and number of children, as well as demographic variables such as age, education, sex, and race. Furthermore, the model incorporates economic controls, including wage income, nonwage income, occupation, rural status, and whether the individual resided in a community property state. To account for industry and geographic influences, we also include industry and state or county fixed effects.

Table 4 presents the main results. Column 1 reports a model with only the 1940 tax burden variable and industry and state fixed effects. As expected, the 1940 tax burden is positively correlated with the likelihood of transitioning to self-employment. In Column 2,

² Taxes have been calculated based on the individual's wage income, as well as their personal and family circumstances. A comprehensive explanation of the tax estimation process can be found in the Appendix.

Table 4
Benchmark models.

VARIABLES	(1) Logit	(2) Logit	(3) Logit	(4) LPM	(5) LPM
Tax_1940	0.00,464*** (0.000258)	0.00336*** (0.000202)	0.00405*** (0.000524)	0.000538*** (1.15e-05)	0.000439*** (1.15e-05)
Tax42_1940					
Wage			-2.16e-05* (1.23e-05)	-2.54e-06*** (1.74e-07)	2.77e-06*** (1.78e-07)
Communityprop		0.380*** (0.00597)	0.378*** (0.00661)		
Incnonwg		0.257*** (0.0129)	0.256*** (0.0125)	0.0364*** (0.000332)	0.0351*** (0.000332)
Married		0.228*** (0.0153)	0.237*** (0.0128)	0.0281*** (0.000283)	0.0257*** (0.000283)
Nchild		0.00599** (0.00277)	0.00627** (0.00282)	0.000764*** (7.09e-05)	0.000402*** (7.09e-05)
Sex		-0.676*** (0.0212)	-0.689*** (0.0241)	-0.0640*** (0.00322)	-0.0614*** (0.00324)
Age		-0.00706*** (0.00122)	-0.00679*** (0.00130)	-0.000831*** (1.09e-05)	-0.000785*** (1.10e-05)
Elementary		-0.0990*** (0.0330)	-0.0993*** (0.0330)	-0.0118*** (0.000618)	-0.00939*** (0.000631)
HS_attending		-0.00800 (0.0411)	-0.00414 (0.0414)	-0.000860 (0.000603)	0.00115* (0.000618)
High_school		0.0790* (0.0427)	0.0856** (0.0433)	0.00996*** (0.000645)	0.0116*** (0.000662)
College_attending		0.194*** (0.0394)	0.202*** (0.0396)	0.0255*** (0.000755)	0.0256*** (0.000769)
College		0.136*** (0.0323)	0.149*** (0.0316)	0.0183*** (0.000805)	0.0186*** (0.000819)
Black		-0.338*** (0.0360)	-0.343*** (0.0366)	-0.0422*** (0.000457)	-0.0401*** (0.000466)
Asian		0.00473 (0.0769)	-0.000101 (0.0769)	0.00374 (0.00518)	-0.0113** (0.00528)
Race_other		-0.133 (0.222)	-0.136 (0.222)	-0.0156 (0.0309)	-0.0108 (0.0309)
Farm_status		0.738*** (0.0308)	0.734*** (0.0307)	0.118*** (0.000452)	0.1000*** (0.000466)
Professionals		-0.0804*** (0.0210)	-0.0728*** (0.0188)	-0.0111*** (0.000525)	-0.0141*** (0.000526)
Managers		0.391*** (0.0223)	0.406*** (0.0199)	0.0579*** (0.000552)	0.0524*** (0.000552)
Clerical		-0.216*** (0.0162)	-0.212*** (0.0152)	-0.0205*** (0.000330)	-0.0193*** (0.000330)
Sales		0.356*** (0.0329)	0.361*** (0.0314)	0.0509*** (0.000512)	0.0489*** (0.000511)
Constant	-2.125*** (0.013,984)	-2.216*** (0.0690)	-2.211*** (0.0679)	0.117*** (0.000950)	0.117*** (0.000950)
Observations	12,764,581	12,312,052	12,312,052	12,312,052	12,312,052
Industry FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
State FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
County FE	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
Log lik	-5.258e+06	-4.968e+06	-4.968e+06		
Pseudo R2	0.0283	0.0485	0.0486		
R-squared				0.0432	0.050

after introducing most control variables, the coefficient for the tax burden remains largely unchanged, positive and highly significant. Marital status and the number of children also have positive and significant coefficients. These two factors indicate that the logic of forming a family partnership, which enables the inclusion of relatives as “silent” partners, played a role in the shift in employment

status. The model also yields additional insights. For example, individuals with higher education levels have greater odds of transitioning to self-employment, and those in managerial or sales occupations are also more likely to make this transition.

In Column 3, wages are added as a control variable. The results show that the positive effect of taxes on the likelihood of transitioning to self-employment remains consistent regardless of the individual's wage level. Indeed, wages appear to be negatively correlated with the probability of a change in labor status. Columns 4 and 5 present linear probability models to simplify the interpretation of the coefficients and incorporate county fixed effects.³ Column 4 uses the same variables as Model 3, whereas Column 5 replaces state fixed effects with county fixed effects. The results show that a \$100 increase in taxes is associated with an average 5 % increase in the likelihood of transitioning to self-employment. Furthermore, Model 5 confirms that the relationship between the 1940 tax burden and the transition to self-employment is not driven by unobserved county-specific factors.

In the Appendix we present various specifications as robustness checks. Notably, the positive correlation between taxes and the transition to self-employment remains consistent, even when the tax burden is modified to factor in the increases in the following years, that is, by using the 1942 tax rates while holding wages at their 1939 levels. Additional checks were performed by excluding agricultural workers or women from the analysis.

To better understand the impact of taxes on the transition to self-employment, Fig. 5 displays the predicted probabilities for individuals with representative tax burdens. The difference is striking: the likelihood of transitioning increases from <15 % to 41 % when comparing an average person who paid no taxes with an individual facing the maximum tax burden that can be computed with census data in 1939 (that is, \$360). More specifically, the predicted probability begins to rise significantly once taxes exceed \$80, which corresponds to the amount an individual with a high salary (above the 95th percentile) or a dual-income couple (both earning relatively high salaries, i.e., above the 80th percentile) would have paid.

4.3. Reassessing wage inequality

The previous sections argued that a significant number of highly paid salary workers changed their employment status during the 1940s. In this last section, we estimate the effect of including the labor earnings of proprietors to assess whether the main trends of the Great Compression are still in place. To calibrate the importance of high-earning proprietors, we follow a similar logic as in the previous sections, integrating national accounts, census records, and tax statistics. However, as previously explained, individual information on proprietors' income appeared for the first time in 1950, with the usual top-coding limit, but was absent from the 1940 census. We turn to tax records to fill the gap in terms of proprietors' earnings in that year by using SOI reports, which include comprehensive data on the income of sole proprietors and partners by industry for some specific years. In this section, we exclude agricultural workers, as tax data are unreliable for measuring farmers' incomes (United States. Office of Business Economics 1953).

In this article, we follow a logic similar to that of some recent papers on this issue (Smith et al. 2019). Using the unique 1953 SOI report on partnerships, which included information on both income and balance sheets at the industry level, we calculate the rate of return of partnerships (net income divided by the capital of partners). In the second step, we compute the capital share of partnership profits by assuming that it should be equal to the return on equity (ROE) for corporations in the same industry. The residual share of profits represents the labor return. The results of this exercise are presented in the Appendix and align with the conventional assumption that labor constitutes approximately 70 % of proprietors' income. However, this approach enables the computation of substantial variations across industries, ranging from 47 % in sectors more intensive in physical capital and natural resources (e.g., mining) to up to 87 % in those more dependent on human capital (e.g., professional services). Given their consistency, these labor/capital ratios are extended to all proprietors (both sole proprietors and partners) for the two census years.

With these coefficients, we can then estimate a new labor earnings distribution that incorporates both the wages and labor income of proprietors. In the 1950 census, merging wage earners and proprietors is a straightforward exercise that only requires imputing incomes above the top-coded level. The 1939 estimate combines tax data from sole proprietorships and partnerships, together with census data on wages.⁴

Fig. 6 depicts the percentage of wage earners and proprietors within the newly computed top decile of the labor earnings distribution in both years.⁴ The results clearly indicate that proprietors were overrepresented at the very top of the labor income distribution. Self-employed individuals represented approximately 14 % of the nonfarm workforce in both years, and their share hovered between 10 % and 12 % of the earners placed between the 90th and the 96th percentiles. In addition, their relative weight hardly increased in these percentiles after the Second World War; thus, the expansion of proprietors was concentrated in the top 3 % of the wage distribution.

Fig. 7 represents the share of proprietors in the top 1 % of the labor income distribution in both benchmark years, thereby confirming the significant change in the relative weight of the two groups. In the 1939 earnings distribution, proprietors constituted 28 % of the top 1 % of the nonfarm working population, but ten years later, this share experienced a substantial upsurge to 41 %.

³ The two most commonly cited flaws of the linear probability model (i.e., "impossible" predictions and nonlinear effects) do not appear to pose significant issues in our model (Hellevik 2009). As shown in Fig. 5, the predicted probabilities remain within the valid range of 0 to 1, and the relationship between the tax burden variable and the likelihood of transition appears largely linear. In addition to simplifying the model's interpretation, the linear probability model enables the inclusion of county fixed effects, which would be computationally challenging in a logit model, given the dataset spans 3,097 U.S. counties.

⁴ This figure utilizes the 99th percentile corresponding to the new labor earnings distribution. These percentiles increased from \$5,246 and \$8,950 to \$5,869 and \$11,249 in 1939 and 1949, respectively.

Fig. 5. Predicted probabilities of transitioning to self-employment by tax level.

Furthermore, when these shares are decomposed at the industry level, proprietors constituted, in some cases, most workers at the top of the distribution. This is the case, for example, in professional services before the war. In the postwar years, the increase in the share of self-employed individuals occurred across all industries. Indeed, in those sectors that started with a high share of wage employment—such as manufacturing, transportation, and finance—the percentage of highly paid proprietors increased more rapidly, doubling their share in this ten-year period.

This evidence is helpful for reevaluating the position of top earners and wage inequality during the Great Compression. Taking this broader definition of labor earnings, we reestimate the average income of the major groups of interest—the top 1 %, next 4 %, and bottom 95 %—as well as their corresponding shares. Table 5 compares these results with the previous estimates that were built by considering only wages and the wage-earning population. The inclusion of self-employed individuals provides two significant changes. First, the notion that the incomes of top-earning workers barely increased over the 1940s due to price and wage controls (Piketty and Saez 2003) is challenged. In the standard analysis that includes only wages, the top 1 % experienced a loss in real terms, whereas the next 4 % experienced sluggish growth in earnings. In contrast, when adjusting for proprietors' labor incomes, both groups experienced an additional increase of approximately 20 % in their cumulative real earnings growth (with the top 1 % growing 12.2 % and the next 4 % increasing 27 %). This change in magnitude is relevant for reconciling the fortune of top earners with the boom in the U.S. economy and the substantial increase in labor productivity over the decade.

The second major conclusion is helpful for calibrating the extent of the Great Compression. Overall, by focusing only on wage workers, scholars have significantly overestimated the decline in inequality during this critical period. Including the self-employed does not change this trend but does significantly reduce its magnitude. The decline in the top 1 % share is reduced by 0.6 percentage points (that is, from a reduction of 30 % to 21 %), and the next 4 % also witnessed a significant change of 0.5 percentage points (or from a decrease of 20 % to 15 %). This evidence ultimately highlights the exceptional performance of workers at the bottom—rather than the poor performance of the top—as the ultimate cause of the Great Compression.

5. Conclusion

This paper examines wage inequality by using tax records, censuses, and other administrative data, analyzing the critical period spanning from the conclusion of the First World War to 1949. The results confirm the extent of a large decline in wage inequality during the 1940s—the Great Compression—identified by previous generations of scholars but provide a more comprehensive account of the secular dynamics and the causes of this sudden shock.

The results of our analysis show that high levels of wage inequality were a constant feature of the interwar period (1918–39), with no evidence of a long-term levelling trend. Tax records indicate that different groups across the wage distribution performed differently during the business cycle. The top 1 % was the group that fared better during the Roaring Twenties but later experienced a substantial contraction in earnings during the Great Depression. In contrast, the next 4 % exhibited stronger wage stickiness, and their relative situation improved during times of crisis (1920–1 and 1929–33). The share of the bottom 95 % stagnated during the 1920s and declined markedly during the first years of the Depression due to the impact of unemployment and wage cuts. In the 1940s, these trends were strongly reversed, as the bottom 95 % significantly outperformed all the other groups.

Fig. 6. The top decile of the nonfarm working population by percentile and employment status, 1939 and 1949. *Source:* SOI (1939) and IPUMS (1940 and 1950). *Note:* Figures on the number of workers are provided for the 90th, 95th and 99th percentiles.

For a better understanding of this process, tax records are supplemented with other sources that allow us to reconcile top wage groups with specific occupations. This analysis illustrates that officers and managers of small and mid-size corporations play a significant role in the decline of the top 1 %. This was mainly due to a shift in preferences regarding the legal status of companies that started to take place from 1939 onward, when an unprecedented rise in corporate tax rates fueled a shift toward the formation of partnerships. This change thereby altered the employment status of the highest-paid salaried workers, turning many highly skilled workers (managers and officers) into proprietors. When factoring in this process, we find that the performance of top earners was better than previously noted, as they adjusted their incomes upward despite war labor regulations. Moreover, this work demonstrates that this shift overstates the decline in wage inequality during the Great Compression. The drops in the top 1 % and the next 4 % earnings share are reduced by 0.6 and 1 percentage point, respectively, when the self-employed are incorporated.

This study has broader implications, as it connects two topics that have often been considered separately: wage inequality and business preferences regarding their legal status. It argues that levels of wage inequality are influenced by private businesses’ decisions

Fig. 7. Percentages of wage earners and self-employed within the Top 1 % of labor earnings, 1939 and 1949.

Source: SOI and IPUMS (1940 and 1950 census). Notes: Only workers with positive wages or self-employed incomes were included. In 1949, workers with dual incomes (both wages and self-employed income) were categorized on the basis of their self-classified employment status.

Table 5

Labor inequality measures for incomes reported in 1939 and 1949 in the non-farm sector.

	Wages			Wages and labor income of the self-employed		
	1939	1949	Real cumulative growth	1939	1949	Real cumulative growth
Panel A: Average income (nominal dollars)						
Bottom 95 %	909	2199	71 %	909	2243	76 %
Next 4 %	3305	5912	8 %	3560	7054	27 %
Top 1 %	10,835	17,378	−11 %	11,896	21,816	12 %
Panel B: Shares						
	1939	1949	Percentage change 1939–49	1939	1949	Percentage change 1939–49
Bottom 95 %	78,3 %	83,6 %	7 %	77,1 %	81,3 %	5 %
Next 4 %	11,9 %	9,5 %	−20 %	12,3 %	10,4 %	−16 %
Top 1 %	9,7 %	6,8 %	−30 %	10,6 %	8,3 %	−21 %

Source: IPUMS census sample (Ruggles et al. 2024) and Statistics of Income.

Note: Estimates of wage inequality (left side) are derived from the established connection between census and tax records, as explained in previous sections. For 1949, we start with the wage distribution from the census and apply a constant upscaling factor to wages that were top-coded at \$10,000, based on SOI data. Estimates of wages and labor income for the self-employed (right side) combine the prior wage distribution with the estimated labor income of proprietors. These estimates are explained at the beginning of this section and rely on a combination of personal income tax records, partnership returns, and census data.

to organize as corporations (resulting in highly paid officers) or as partnerships (resulting in proprietors earning a mixed income that falls outside the scope of most studies). Consequently, significant shifts in these preferences should be taken into account, and scholars should strive to uncover the complexities imposed by these legal definitions. A promising avenue of research would involve gaining a better understanding of whether differences in top wage shares between countries are determined by the substantial variations in the relative prevalence of corporations. For instance, if corporations were much more important in the United States than in other advanced economies at the beginning of the 20th century—as illustrated by Hannah (2015)—it would follow that the observed disparities in wage inequality levels could be partly attributed to this factor.

Moreover, the legal form of business has significant social implications when the contributions of labor and capital income to overall income inequality are examined. Most studies that analyze the joint distribution of these two income sources begin in the post-WWII period (Berman and Milanovic 2024), often projecting backward in time an idealized view of a rentier society, where workers and capitalists were distinct groups. The findings presented here offer a fresh perspective on the interplay between labor and capital in the first half of the 20th century, challenging conventional notions about their roles during this period.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Miguel Artola Blanco: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Victor Manuel Gómez-Blanco:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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